

Schematic representation of the relative amount of mRNA under submerged condition. Numerals represent the relative amounts of transcript as a percentage of the untreated samples: (1) phosphoglucosomerase, (2) phosphofruktokinase, (3) aldolase, (4) triose phosphate isomerase (5) triose phosphate dehydrogenase, (6) phosphoglyceric kinase, (7) enolase, (8) pyruvic kinase, (9) Pyruvic decarboxylase, (10) alcohol dehydrogenase, (11) Dihydroliopyl transacetylase (12) isocitric dehydrogenase, (13) succinyl/CoA synthetase, (14) succinic dehydrogenase, (iron-sulfur protein subunit), (15) succinic dehydrogenase (flavoprotein subunit).

under osmotic (6% or 20% sucrose), saline (2% NaCl), or N-starvation stresses. More than 2,000 cDNA clones were partially sequenced and compared with the GenBank and EMBL data bases. This allowed about 10% of the cDNA clones to be putatively identified as particular genes. These results indicate that stress treatment of suspension cultured cells makes it possible to effi-

ciently isolate various types of plant genes.

To examine the usefulness of expressed sequence tags (ESTs) for the study of gene expression in a specific metabolic pathway, we analyzed transcript levels of genes engaged in ATP-generating pathways under submergence stress. We quantified each transcript level of genes associated with glycolysis and alcoholic fermentation

several times under submergence stress. We found two types of induction patterns: Type I and Type II.

Maximum expression of Type I genes occurred after 24 h of submergence. Transfer to aerobic condition or partial exposure of shoot tips to air reduced expression. In the submergence-tolerant rice cultivar FR13A, several Type I genes were highly induced compared with intolerant cultivar IR42. This suggests that Type I genes may play an essential role in the activation of glycolysis and alcohol fermentation under submerged condition.

Transcripts of Type II genes, such as aldolase and pyruvate kinase genes, reached the maximum after 10 h and did not show remarkable decrease by transfer to aerobic condition. These results suggest that expression of Type I and Type II genes is differentially regulated under low oxygen condition.

It would be worthwhile to analyze mechanisms associated with coordinate or differential expression of the genes. This will lead to improved understanding in molecular breeding of means to manipulate a whole metabolic pathway in rice plants. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Mapping of genes responsible for cold tolerance at the booting stage of rice

A. Kato, K. Saito, K. Nagano, K. Miura, and H. Araki, Hokkaido National Agricultural Experiment Station, Hitsujigaoka 1, Toyohira-ku, Sapporo 062, Japan

Norin PL 8 is a cold-tolerant parental rice line. It was developed by introducing the genes for cold tolerance from a javanica rice, Silewah, into a Japanese cultivar, Hokkai 241. The chromosome segments introgressed into Norin PL 8 from Silewah have been mapped on chromosomes 1, 3, 4, 7, and 8, and the loci on chromosomes 3 and 4 are probably involved in cold tolerance (Saito et al 1995).

The fertility of B_1F_4 plants of Norin PL 8 and Kirara 397 (Kirara 397/Norin PL 8//

Kirara 397) was 0-95% in the field in 1993. The temperature at booting stage was 2-3 °C lower than that in the average year.

We analyzed the restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) patterns and fertility of 47 selected B_1F_4 plants. Fertility of the plants showing Silewah-type patterns for the loci of chromosome 3 or 4 was about 10% higher than for those plants with Hok-

kai 241-type patterns (see table). The results were almost the same as those obtained in a cold water experiment in which plants in a field were irrigated with cold water for about 1 mo, from the early stages of panicle formation to heading (Saito et al 1995), confirming that the loci on chromosomes 3 and 4 are involved in cold tolerance.

Genotype and fertility of B_1F_4 plants^a of Kirara 397/Norin-PL8//Kirara 397 in 1993.

RFLP marker	Chromosome	Fertility (%)		
		Kirara-type	Heterozygote	Silewah-type
XNpb100	3	50.4	59.0	63.8
XNpb345	3	50.5	56.9	63.8
XNpb102	4	50.6	68.4	66.1
XNpb235	4	52.5	65.1	66.8
XNpb177	4	52.5	65.1	66.8
XNpb379	7	51.2	-	66.8
XNpb278	8	58.7	46.0	57.9

^aPlants (n = 47) were selected from 500 plants; different fertility classes are nearly equally represented. The temperature during July and August 1993 was 2-3 °C lower than that for the average year. The fertility of Kirara 397 was 40%.

Rice parental lines Hokkai PL 5, Hokkai PL 6, and Hokkai PL 7 are also cold-tolerant lines developed using the same procedures, except that the genes from javanica rice Lambayque 1, Mitak, and Thangone were introduced into Hokkai 244, the japonica parent. RFLP patterns of these parental lines indicated that the genes from javanica parents are located at least on chromosomes 1, 5, 10, and 11 in Hokkai PL 5, on chromosomes 8 and 10 in Hokkai PL 6, and on chromosomes 4, 5, and 7 in Hokkai PL 7. On the other hand, the RFLP markers for the loci on chromosomes 3 and 4 where the genes involved in cold tolerance in Norin PL 8 are located showed Hokkai 244- type patterns, suggesting that the genes involved in cold tolerance in Hokkai PL 5, Hokkai PL 6, and Hokkai PL 7 are different from those of Norin PL 8.

Cited reference

Saito K, Miura K, Nagano K, Hayano-Saito Y, Siato A, Araki H, Kato A. 1995. Chromosome location of quantitative trait loci for cool tolerance at the booting stage in rice variety 'Norin-PL8'. *Breed Sci.* 45:337-340. ■

1. Fine-striped leaf (top) and normal leaf (bottom).

Variation in leaf color and thylakoid protein analyzed in chlorophyll rice mutant

C. Aoki, Y. Imai, A. Furuta, T. Nishimura, and K. Hattori, Laboratory of Plant Genetics and Breeding, School of Agricultural Sciences, Nagoya University, Chikusa, Nagoya 464-01, Japan

Some strains of chlorophyll-deficient mutants albina, viridis, chlorona, virescence, and zebra, obtained by δ -ray irradiation of rice, are preserved in our laboratory. We studied the modified leaf color and thylakoid protein of a low temperature-sensitive, chlorophyll-deficient rice mutant.

The mutant was derived from the *Oryza sativa* cultivar Nipponbare, which was irradiated by δ -ray at the total dose of 40 Gy (0.8 d^{-1}). Seeds of the mutant and normal Nipponbare were sprouted at 30°C . At the 3d-leaf stage, seedlings were transferred to a phytotron in which they were exposed to controlled day-night temperatures of 30-24, 25-19, and 24-14 $^\circ\text{C}$

2. Polypeptides of thylakoid protein from the leaf blade of doubled haploid Nipponbare (C) and mutant (M) grown at 30-24 $^\circ\text{C}$ (H), 25-19 $^\circ\text{C}$ (M), and 20-14 $^\circ\text{C}$ (L) in a phytotron. In the lanes of the mutant, closed arrows point to missing or faint bands in fine-striped and white leaves, arrowheads point to missing or faint bands in white leaves only, and open arrows point to added or intensified bands compared with patterns of green leaves.